

Disc Springs – A useful utility in cyclic stressed steel connections

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ABSTRACT

Bolted connections are often required as a force connection to transmit tension forces only. However, constructing such connections precisely as pure tension joints - without any restraint moments -, is structurally impossible. This is a key problem for bolted tension-force-connections in cyclic loaded structures. In these connections, rotations of connected structural members, induced by cyclic loads on the structure, enforce deformations and therefore high additional cyclic stresses in the bolts. Therefore, the bolts are highly fatigue stressed and will frequently fail at an early stage. Disc springs are excellent structural elements in order to make fatigue-resistant tension-force-connections. They can be stacked in series (discs layered in alternate directions) or stacked in parallel (discs layered in same direction) or in a combination of both (stacks of disc spring stacked in parallel to be stacked in series). Therefore, the characteristic curve of the whole spring unit can be designed as required. Rotations of connected structural elements will be compensated by the spring structure and do not enforce relevant deformations of the bolts. The stress amplitude in the bolts can be adjusted to a required level by the use of disc spring elements.

Unfortunately, the useful features of disc springs and the knowledge of how to design disc spring units are not very well known in the structural steel industry. This paper will close this gap in information to a certain degree. In addition, special information on rules and conditions for structural design and some realized examples will be given.

Keywords: disc spring, tension-force-connection, cyclic stress, fatigue design

1 INTRODUCTION

Disc springs have been known since the 19th century and have been used ever since. However, at that early time it was not yet possible to calculate them. It took up to the year 1936 before a suitable approximation method for calculating conical annular shells was published. The possibility to calculate disc springs with reasonable effort laid the foundation for the widespread use of them as a construction element, particularly after the Second World War. (1).

Furthermore, several different papers on the calculation of disc springs were published for many years in succession. In 1983, Niepage (2) compared the various calculation methods. For practical application, the differences in the calculation theories are negligible compared to the manufacturing tolerances and the influences of measurement errors in production control.

In Germany, disc springs were standardized early in 1957 within DIN 2093 (2). A separate standard, DIN 2092, was published for the calculation. These two standards were adapted several times over the years and were replaced by the two European standards EN 16983 (3) and EN 16984 (4). The standard ISO 19690-1 (5) for the calculation and the standard ISO 19690-2 (6) for the technical specifications are also available for international use.

The main advantages of the disc springs include (1):

- Multiplication of the load capacity by simple parallel stacking of disc springs
- Multiplication of the deflection by simple stacking of disc springs in alternating orientation
- High fatigue strength of the steel disc springs
- Progressive load-deflection curves are possible by stacking disc springs with different thicknesses in alternating orientation or by stacking disc spring stacks with a different number of disc springs stacked in parallel
- Small construction space for small deflections with high load capacities

Disc springs are used in a wide range of applications. Areas of application are for example plant engineering, power plant construction and mechanical engineering. Their range of applications extends from use in small devices (such as drills) to bearings for large plant components (such as boilers in power plants). Due to their properties, there are cases in steel structures where their use is appropriate, sensible and recommended. Examples of this include the anchoring of crane runway girders in bearings of intermediate supports and tension-force-connections with high-tension bolts in case that deformations of interconnected components induce constraining forces into the bolts.

In this paper, we provide a brief introduction to designing with disc springs. Chapter 2 of this paper describes the main properties and further the possible combinations of disc springs. Chapter 3 provides information on calculation of disc springs and disc spring systems. Special important design guidelines are discussed in chapter 4. Finally, some examples of possible applications are shown in chapter 5.

2 TECHNICAL PROPERTIES

Disc springs are conical annular shells, see *Fig 1*. The spring effect is a reaction of the conical annular shell, when a load F - as shown in *Fig. 1a* - is applied. Disc springs are standardized. The standard EN 16983 (3) applies to the quality requirements and the standard EN 16984 (4) to the design criteria and calculation. Very detailed manuals are provided from the various manufacturers (7), (8), (9), (10). Brief descriptions of disc springs can also be found in (11) and (12).

Fig. 1. a) Single disc spring (sectional view) cf. EN 16984 (4) Fig. 1 b) 3D-view of a single disc spring

2.1 Standardized Properties

Standardized disc springs according to EN 16983 (3) are classified into the three dimensional series A, B and C, see *Table 1*. Each series is moreover subdivided into three manufacturing groups 1, 2 and 3, which is a classification regarding the shell thickness. Series A includes hard disc springs, series B soft disc springs and series C very soft disc springs. There are disc springs with and without flat bearings as it is shown in *Fig 1a* and *Table 2*.

Table 1. Classes of Disc Springs according to (3) table 3

Dimensional Series	h_0/t
A	approximately 0.40
B	approximately 0.70
C	≈ 1.30

Fig. 2. Main dimensions of a single disc spring

Table 2. Groups of Disc Springs according to (3) table 2

Group	t [mm]	with flat bearings and reduced thickness
1	< 1.25	no
2	$1.25 \leq t \leq 6$	no
3	$6 < t \leq 14$	yes

2.2 Properties of Single Disc Springs

Disc springs are made of quenched and tempered steel. They are able to absorb high forces with at the same time small spring deflections. Furthermore, they have good suspension properties and a high working capacity in the area of $1.7 \leq \delta \leq 2.5$, with $\delta = \frac{D_e}{D_i}$.

The load-deflection curve for a single disc spring is a nonlinear function. The curvature depends on the ratio $\frac{h_0}{t}$ (see Table 1, Fig. 3a). Hence, the spring stiffness varies more or less with the spring deflection s . The disc spring is in flattened position, when the spring deflection s equals h_0 . For static loads the spring deflection of the standardized disc springs shall be limited to $0.75 h_0$. If $\frac{s}{h_0} > 0.75$, the calculated characteristic load-deflection curve deviates increasingly from the measured load-deflection curve, see Fig. 3b.

In Fig. 3a the blue load-deflection curves delimit the range for the disc springs of dimensional series C (blue area), the green curves delimit the range for the disc springs of dimensional series B (green area) and the black curves delimit the range for the disc springs of dimensional series A (small grey area).

Fig. 3. a) Load-deflection curves for various h_0/t -ratios;
b) actual and design load-deflection curves for a disc spring (EN 16983-B50) taken from EN 16984 (4) Figure 7,
1 actual curve, 2 design curve

2.3 Combination of Disc Springs

Disc springs can be combined in various ways. Therefore, the spring characteristic curve is adaptable to specific requirements. The following combinations are possible:

- *Single disc spring*
- *Several disc springs stacked in series*
*The disc springs are stacked in alternating orientation to form **series stacks**.*
- *Several disc springs stacked in parallel*
*The disc springs are stacked in the same orientation to form **parallel stacks**.*
- *Several **parallel stacks** stacked in series*
*The disc spring stacks are stacked in alternating orientation to form **combined stacks**.*

In the following, **spring stack** refers to one of the above described combination cases, single disc spring, parallel stack, series stack or combined stack. The number of single disc springs stacked in parallel is denoted by **n**. Whereas the number of single disc springs or spring stacks stacked in series is denoted by **i**, see Fig. 4a.

If possible, spring stacks should be designed in a way that an even number of disc springs is reached, see for example Fig 4b. In Fig. 5 is shown, that the load-deflection curve of spring stacks can be adapted as required. Depending on how the disc springs are combined, the required load capacity or the required spring deflection can be adjusted.

In addition, different combinations of layering options within a spring stack generates progressive spring characteristics. Two methods are shown in Fig. 6. On the left, single-disc springs with different thicknesses are used. On the right, different number of single-disc springs are used in the individual parallel stacks.

Fig. 4. a) Possible combinations of disc springs b) series stack with even number i

Fig. 5. a) disc springs stacked in parallel b) disc springs stacked in series

Fig. 6. Various progressive load-deflection curves, taken from EN 16984 (4) Figure 9
 a) disc springs with different thicknesses b) different stackings

3 DESIGN OF SPRING STACKS

Spring stacks can be designed and calculated in accordance EN 16984 (4). For this, certain rules have to be considered.

3.1 Basic Design Rules

In case of dynamic loads, disc springs should be preloaded. A preload of $s_1 \approx 0,15 h_0 \dots 0.20 h_0$ should be provided, see Fig. 7a. Then, the corresponding fatigue verifications must be performed for the load cycle $\Delta s = s_2 - s_1$. The decisive stresses occur at the points I, II, III and IV, shown in Fig 7b.

Fig. 7. a) Spring deflection s_1 and s_2 ; b) key points I, II, III and IV for stress checks

3.2 How to calculate Spring Stacks?

As already mentioned above, spring stacks can be calculated in accordance with EN 16984 (4). The calculation method and the corresponding calculation formulas are given there. In addition, the manufacturers of the disc springs offer calculation programs, usually as Excel files, free of charge. These programs are usually available for download. They can be used to perform detailed design calculations, including fatigue verifications, for all possible combinations of disc springs.

3.3 Effect of Friction

In the diagrams shown so far, the effect of friction has been neglected for simplicity. Nevertheless, friction loads must be taken into account according to EN 16984 (4) chapter 8. Friction acts mainly

- between the conical contact surfaces of the individual disc springs (inter-surface friction),
- between the contact surfaces of the flat plates - between the spring stack is compressed – and the compressed spring stack (edge friction) and
- between spring stack and the guide element.

Therefore, the amount of friction is mainly depending on the number of disc springs and on the properties of the contact surfaces. Friction loads arise, during the spring loading process (increasing the spring load) and during the unloading (decreasing the spring load).

The influence of friction on the characteristic curve during loading and unloading is shown in Fig. 8. The thicker lines indicate the measured curves and the slightly thinner lines the curves calculated with the influence of friction. In Tab. 3 are estimated values given for the effect of friction. Moreover, the effect of friction on the load-deflection curve of a combined spring stack is shown in Fig 9.

Table 3. Effect of friction on the spring force (10)

Spring Stack	Estimated effect size
$n = 1$	\mp (2% to 3%)
$n = 2$	\mp (4% to 6%)
$n = 3$	\mp (6% to 9%)
$n = 4$	\mp (8% to 12%)
$n = 5$	\mp (10% to 15%)

Fig. 8. Comparison of measured and calculated load-deflection curves for a single spring and parallel stacks with $n = 2 \dots 4$, taken from (13) Bild 7

Fig. 9. Cf. (14) Abb. 4.22d a) Spring stack with different stacking b) corresponding load-deflection curve considering the influence of friction

4 SOME DESIGN GUIDELINES

Disc springs always require a guide element to prevent lateral slippage under load. This guide can either be on the inside diameter (guide rod) or on the outer diameter (guide sleeve). In Fig. 10b and in Fig. 11b are examples shown for a guide rod and a guide sleeve. A guide sleeve additionally has the advantage that the disc springs are protected to a certain extend from external influences. A lubrication at the inside of the sleeve is sufficient as corrosion protection. Between the guide element and the spring stack clearance is required. The recommended values for the clearance are shown in Tab. 4 in accordance with EN 16983 (3). In Fig. 10b and in Fig. 11b are examples shown for a guide rod and a guide sleeve.

The guide element and the support must consist of case-hardened materials with an insert depth of approximately 0.8 mm and a minimum hardness of 60 HRC. The surface of the guide element should be smooth and flawless. Unhardened guide elements are also permissible for disk springs subjected to static loads. (3).

Table 4. Recommended clearance between spring stack and guide element

D_i or D_e	Total clearance c acc. to (3)
$\leq 16 \text{ mm}$	0.2 mm
$16 \text{ mm} < c \leq 20 \text{ mm}$	0.3 mm
$20 \text{ mm} < c \leq 26 \text{ mm}$	0.4 mm
$26 \text{ mm} < c \leq 31.5 \text{ mm}$	0.5 mm
$31.5 \text{ mm} < c \leq 50 \text{ mm}$	0.6 mm
$50 \text{ mm} < c \leq 80 \text{ mm}$	0.8 mm
$80 \text{ mm} < c \leq 140 \text{ mm}$	1.0 mm
$140 \text{ mm} < c \leq 250 \text{ mm}$	1.6 mm

Further detailed design instructions and information on corrosion protection can be found in the manufacturer's manuals.

5 FIELD OF APPLICATION

This chapter contains a few examples of disc spring applications in steel construction.

5.1 Disc Spring Insulation of a Factory Ceiling

Disc springs are also an ideal construction element for insulating components, for example against impacts. As mentioned before, they only require a small construction volume for small deflections with high load capacities. See for example *Fig. 10*.

Fig. 10. Disc spring insulation of a factory ceiling, taken from (1) Bild 11

5.2 Disc Springs in Tunnel Construction

A construction of spring stacks was installed in a correspondingly modified tunnel cross-section. The tunnel tube consists of sheet steel corrugated in the direction of the tunnel. Excessive subsidence of the tunnel ridge and the associated damage to the buildings located directly above the tunnel could be avoided thanks to the modified construction with disc springs. See (15).

5.3 Disc Springs in Beam-to-Column Connections

The paper (16) reports on research for the use of disc springs in friction sliding structural connections to prevent bolt tension loss of fully tensioned bolts due to earthquake actions.

5.4 Support Anchoring of Continuous Crane Runway Girders

With heavy crane operation and larger spans, continuous girders are oftentimes requested for operational reasons for the use as crane runways. In the case of single-span girders, a sharp buckling occurs at the supports due to end support rotations. This leads to unsteady driving behaviour of the cranes and possibly to damage to the rail clamps and horizontal bearings.

On the other hand, anchoring the intermediate supports of continuous girders is generally problematic. Anchor bolts are always located at a certain distance from the support axis. For this reason, they always receive large imposed tensile forces when the beam bends under load – e.g. due to crane travel – and thus rotates at the support. As a consequence, the anchor bolts usually fail within a short time (fatigue fracture) in case of frequent crane operation. See *Fig. 11a* for example. The problem can be covered by the use of disc springs. They ensure that the tension force in the bolts remains approximately constant.

Fig 11b shows an example for the use of spring stacks for a repair of anchor bolts embedded in concrete. The anchor bolts had failed due to fatigue fracture. In contrast, *Fig 12* shows an example, where spring stacks are already part of the design.

Fig. 11. a) Fatigue fracture in an anchor bolt b) usage of spring stacks for a repair of anchor bolts embedded in concrete

Fig. 12. a) Anchoring of crane runway girder on steel console with the use of spring stacks (see black sleeve) b) corresponding vertical cross section through the sleeve and the spring stack

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